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Nigeria's Compliance with the Yaoundé Code of Conduct in the Cases of Piracy and Armed Piracy of the Nigerian State in the Gulf of Guinea in 2016-2021

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Abstract

Through adherence to the Yaoundé Code of Conduct and its execution in eradicating piracy and armed piracy instances that happened in the Gulf of Guinea from 2016 to 2021, this study evaluates Nigeria's history, progress, and response to piracy. The goal of this study is to examine Nigeria's compliance with the Yaoundé Code of Conduct as shown in its papers and historical development in accordance with the documentation from the literature review. The data was processed using qualitative approaches, namely research on descriptive research, which focuses on employing analysis to provide an overview or description of a scenario. The information received is analyzed utilizing non-reactive research methods after being gleaned from pertinent literature investigations. This approach will process information from reliable sources, including primary and secondary data, which will then be examined in accordance with predetermined theories and concepts to provide a response to the problem formulation. According to the study's findings, from 2016 to 2021, Nigeria adhered to the Yaounde Code of Conduct in situations of piracy and armed piracy. Nigeria is actively creating and putting into effect a national maritime security strategy to safeguard its marine affairs from all kinds of illegal activity. In compliance with the Yaounde Code of Conduct, Nigeria enacted the POMO ACT which made Nigeria the first country with an anti-piracy law and cooperated in the protection of vessels in accordance with the articles contained in the Yaounde Code of Conduct. However, Nigeria's strict emphasis on adhering to the Yaounde Code of Conduct hasn't worked to stop piracy because it doesn't deal with the underlying issues.

Keywords: Gulf of Guinea, Nigeria, Piracy, Yaounde Code of Conduct

1. Introduction

The current threats to maritime security are associated with the development of non-traditional security, where the threat has taken the form of an expansion of threats that no longer only concern militaristic threats or interactions between state actors but also non-state actors, terrorist organizations, and individual terrorists. Maritime conflicts between nations, marine terrorism, piracy, drug trafficking, illegal immigration, the spread of weaponry, illegal fishing, environmental crimes, and maritime disasters are all examples of maritime hazards (Broohm et al., 2020).

Because of how concerning this act of piracy is, officials must be able to distinguish it from maritime terrorism in order to create and implement effective remedies (Nelson, 2012).

Illegal, Unregulated, and Unreported (IUU) Fishing refers to fishing activities in the territory of another country, using equipment that is prohibited or harmful to the environment and failing to record the catch. In addition, maritime economic interests include several important components such as preservation of fishing and freshwater resources, development of port facilities for logistics purposes, reduction of crime and illegal control, improvement of trade routes security, promotion of tourism development, and protection of ecosystems (Juned et al., 2022).

Piracy and armed piracy are caused by maritime hazards in Nigeria, notably in the Gulf of Guinea (Begum et al., 2011). Researcher, decision-makers, and the media have demonstrated concerns during the past ten years that are more concerned with economic, political, and security aspects than with casualties related to such activities (Jimoh, 2015). According to data from the IMB, crimes including piracy, hostage taking, and the murder of crew, passengers, and staff have increased in frequency in Nigeria's coastal seas in addition to armed robberies (Jimoh, 2015). (International Maritime Bureau, 2019).

According to IMB, there were ups and downs in the number of armed robberies and pirate attacks from 2016 to 2021. Zones of concern exist in three geographic regions: the Strait of Malacca, the South China Sea, the Somali Coast, and the Horn of Africa, particularly the Gulf of Guinea, which has been ranked as the third most vulnerable region since 2011 (Fattah, 2017). Since shifting their geographic focus to African waters, particularly the Gulf of Guinea region with high concentrations in the waters of Somalia and Nigeria, maritime pirate activities, which previously focused primarily on pumping activities in Asian countries, have become more prevalent (ONUOHA, 2013). In the past two decades, there have been cases of piracy in the Gulf of Guinea. Cases of piracy in the Gulf of Guinea over the past 2 decades, it was noted that a total of 734 pirate attacks occurred in the region between 1991 and 2012, with Nigeria taking up 46% of the incidents (ONUOHA, 2013).

The Gulf of Guinea is a global pirate hotspot, accounting for 43% of all documented piracy events, due to the rising threat of marine crime off the coast of West Africa (International Maritime Bureau, 2021). According to the IMB, 135 crew men have been kidnapped from their ships worldwide in 2020, with the Gulf of Guinea accounting for more than 95% of those incidents. In addition, 161 ships were taken over, 20 attacks were attempted, and 11 instances of ships being shot at. The IMB reported 38 occurrences of armed robbery and pumping against ships in the first quarter of 2021. (International Maritime Bureau, 2021).

Off the coast of West Africa, the Gulf of Guinea is a section of the eastern tropical Atlantic Ocean. The Volta and Niger rivers are its principal tributaries. Africa's principal trade route is the Volta River, while the Niger River passes through nine nations. Volta and Niger both gained access to the world's marine trade (Petr, 1986). Additionally, the Gulf of Guinea hosts 20 commercial ports and 25% of all maritime trade in Africa. The Gulf of Guinea contains 2.7% of natural gas reserves and 4.5% of petroleum reserves, accounting for 60% of Africa's oil production (Morcos, 2021). However, just a little portion of the revenue from the oil wealth that the people receive as a result of government errors. Lack of employment opportunities and unemployment are the main reason why many people in Nigeria are driving to turn to piracy as a livelihood rather than the sector (Kadafa, 2012).

Insecurity in the Niger Delta is also reportedly linked to crime on land, where grievances over perceived marginalization and ecological degradation have long fueled insecurity. Studies show that piracy tends to be perpetrated or supported by marginalized communities who do not participate in economic development. Poor fishermen in west Africa turned to piracy to amass wealth through ship robbery and piracy, kidnapping crew members and often holding them for ransom (Bueger, 2013).

According to Onouha research from 2012, Nigeria still has significant security challenges. These difficulties are caused by a variety of factors, including extreme poverty, bloody wars, floods and earthquakes, terrorist acts, and external hostility. These challenging circumstances provided a significant and ongoing impetus for the subject of enhancing safety, particularly maritime security. This difficulty makes it difficult for Nigeria to uphold security within its borders, including marine security (Onuoha, 2012).

In a subsequent study by Okoronwo (2014), despite the differences and blurred definitions of Maritime Security in various countries, the weak maritime security in Nigeria does not only stem from the weak definition of maritime security. There are other contributing factors to the state of maritime security in Nigeria such as the deep corruption in Nigeria that makes it very easy for pirates and sea bandits to carry out their illegal activities. Based on this journal, there is more attention to be paid than just the definition of maritime security itself, which is the resolution of the country's problems in Nigeria (Okoronkwo et al., 2014).

Government failure can quickly lead to insecurity on land which can easily spill over into maritime security. Nigeria has experienced an increase in piracy cases due to increasing lawlessness in areas bordering major global shipping routes, desperation among residents, and a lack of government attention to maritime security issues (Pérouse de Montclos, 2012).

As shipping companies struggle to balance consistent demand with escalating expenses in order to secure safe passage and port cooperation in the Gulf of Guinea, maritime economic security is coming under greater danger. There is a lot of travel in this area for Europe, and according to the European Association of Shipowners (ECSA), a ship can be chartered to a non-European country or be owned by a European corporation even though it is sailing under a non-European flag. Products can be transported between African ports and Erop, or European goods everywhere, by non-Eropa vessels (Barrios, 2013). This maritime menace will undoubtedly present challenges in the social and economic spheres (Bowden, 2010).

The weaknesses and inadequacies of the maritime policies of the Gulf of Guinea countries and the lack of cooperation between them have gradually created opportunities for the activities of criminal networks to diversify their activities and expand their networks from the coast of Nigeria to the outer seas (Hasan & Hassan, 2016; Hodgkinson, 2013)

The Yaoundé Code of Ethics was one of the tools developed to address this issue. In an effort to raise the commitment of African leaders to demonstrate political will and set a tone of leadership in the governance of Africa's maritime domain, the Yaoundé Code of Conduct was developed to improve the continent's strategic approach to maritime safety and security. The Yaoundé Code of Conduct will be in effect in Nigeria until 2021, and past studies have shown that this will significantly reduce the amount of piracy and armed robberies in the Gulf of Guinea. The Yaounde Code of Conduct, a measure to combat pirate instances in Nigeria, was created for a number of reasons, which have also been the subject of numerous research. But few studies explain the effectiveness of this code of conduct for reducing piracy in Nigeria. So, this study will analyze Nigeria's compliance with the Yaoundé Code of Conduct in cases of piracy and armed piracy of Nigerian states in the Gulf of Guinea in 2016-2021.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Research Design

This study adopts a *non-reactive research* design. This research design will process data from credible sources such as primary and secondary data which are then analyzed based on predetermined theories or concepts to answer the problem formulation. This method will analyze primary and secondary data derived from literature studies to analyze Nigeria's compliance with the Yaounde Code of Conduct to piracy cases that occurred in Nigeria in 2016-2021.

2.2. Data Collection Methods

In this study, both primary and secondary data were gathered and analyzed. Data were gathered utilizing two different techniques: literature reviews and documentation. A literature study is a method of data collection that uses information obtained from official, unquestionably reliable sources, such as the official website of the institution or organizations, summaries of case study-based high-level conferences, publications of previous research in the form of journals, theses, and dissertations, and well-known news portals from around the world

(Harris, 1995; Todorov & Lyons, 2007). The study that was employed looked at how the Yaounde Code of Conduct was put into action to combat piracy in the Gulf of Guinea.

Researcher will gather a variety of documents relevant to the issue as the source of documentation, including exclusive documents like letters of agreement and case reports to support data as material for study analysis as well as public documents like news, papers, reports, and other public documents like news articles. Researcher can obtain detailed information about the issues in this study relating to the two data gathering methods mentioned above. To serve as a guide and the foundation for this research, data from studies of the literature and documentation will be chosen.

2.3. Data Analysis

All data that has been collected will be selected or reduced through qualitative data analysis. Data reduction is carried out with the aim of directing and classifying data into information that can be used as a final conclusion that can be obtained. Data that has been reduced is drawn in the form of a set of information arranged into a more organized form so that it is easy to understand.

The information presented in this study took the form of data on case numbers or statistics, documents obtained related to the Yaounde Code of Conduct, cases of piracy in Nigeria, and other documents that are relevant to the question of the effectiveness of the Yaounde Code of Conduct in the Nigerian state. The next step is to form conclusions based on the research findings and data validation. To get outcomes that reflect the facts, careful effort is put into drawing conclusions or doing verification. In order to deduce meaning from data and give researcher the chance to get feedback, drawing conclusions requires extensive analysis of data reduction and data display (Iskandar, 2009).

2.4. Concept

Maritime security is any action taken by owners, operators, port facilities, ship administrators, offshore installations, and marine organizations in protecting sea areas from the presence of piracy, theft, confiscation, sabotage and other disturbances (McNicholas, 2016).

Key Concept in Maritime Security: According to Morris & Paoli (2018) and Väyrynen (2022), maritime security is defined as a combination of preventive and responsive measures to safeguard the marine domain against threats and intentional unlawful acts to safeguard the maritime domain against, limit the effects of, accidental or natural hazards, environmental hazards and damage, risks or losses (Morris & Persi Paoli, 2018).

Compliance theory is a theory that explains a condition where individuals obey established rules to avoid the punishment that will be imposed. In this theory there are two perspectives regarding compliance with the law, namely instrumental and normative. On an instrumental perspective, individual compliance is driven by self-interest and responses to changes in *tangible*, incentive and penalties related to behavior. While the normative perspective deals with what is considered moral and opposite to self-interest (Mitchell, 2020).

Compliance and conformance to established norms are closely related concepts. International norms are frequently misinterpreted. Depending on whether they are imposed on actors or voluntarily accepted, norms can differ significantly. Norms may be enforced internally or externally. Exogenous enforcement takes place outside of established norms and institutions, whereas endogenous enforcement is included in international treaties and has the power to impose itself. Negative enforcement is coercive, whereas positive enforcement is convincing and feasible. In general, globalization promotes facilitation and results in the endogenous enforcement of standards (Väyrynen, 2022).

Researcher examined Nigeria's compliance with the Yaoundé Code of Conduct in cases of piracy and armed piracy of Nigerian states in the Gulf of Guinea (Gulf of Guinea) in 2016–2021 using the notion of maritime security based on compliance theory.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Yaounde Code of Conduct

The Yaounde Code of Conduct serves as the foundation for regional maritime security cooperation in the Gulf of Guinea among the Signatory countries. The ECOWAS, ECCAS, and GGC countries' most thorough effort to construct a regional maritime-related security system is the Yaounde Code of Conduct. This Code of Ethics acts as a set of guidelines for maritime-related instruments of cooperation and has the potential to be a rule of conduct (Nwangwu et al., 2015). Yaounde's Code of Conduct tackles the majority of maritime insecurity causes in the area, including money laundering, drugs and weapons trafficking, oil theft, human trafficking, people smuggling, illegally caught and disposed of fish, maritime terrorism, hostage-taking, piracy and armed robbery at sea (Anabia-Tiah, 2022).

3.2. Nigeria's Compliance With Yaounde's Code of Conduct

3.2.1. Ship Protection Cooperation

In accordance with article 4 of the Yaounde Code of Conduct, in complying with the Yaounde Code of Conduct Nigeria in April 2016 launched the Nigerian Navy's anti-piracy operation code named "*Operation Tsare Teku*" (Abuja, 2017). *Operation Tsare Teku I-III* was a special naval operation aimed at ridding the country of armed robbery, pipeline vandalism and to protect local merchant ships and international includes containing the threat of piracy and attacks on shipping and oil and gas installations. The operation focuses on outside the main offshore waters of Nigeria supported by the Nigerian Navy (Obi & Oriola, 2018). This operation began in 2016 until January 2017.

In order to safeguard Nigeria's marine shipping and security, Operation Tsare Teku was successful in lowering instances of pipeline damage, armed robberies, and other offshore criminal activity (Nwatu, 2022). Piracy and hostage-taking in Nigerian waters were successfully decreased during Operation Tsare Teku II's second phase. According to a report by Global Security, there were just 2 instances of piracy and armed piracy in Nigeria up until July 2016 (Ayoyo & Oriola, 2018). Operation Tsare Teku III, however, did not have a substantial effect until the end of 2016, when the number of reported cases of piracy increased to 36 from 14 in 2015.

On June 24, 2016, *Operation Delta Safe* was also conducted. Operation Delta Safe is part of the Nigerian Defense Headquarters initiative to restructure the Joint Task Force in the delivery of services, efficiency and effectiveness of Nigeria's greater maritime security provision well (Agim, 2018). The operation, which was deployed at Cross River, led to the killing of 7 militants linked to the pirate action and thwarted and arrested 2 suspected pirates who later captured Another 8 suspects (Sahara Reporters, 2016).

In addition, *Sharkbite Exercise* operation in November 2016 and *Operation Rivers Sweep I-II* in January 2017 were also carried out (Punchng, 2020). However, the maritime space security improvements made throughout 2017 by the Nigerian Navy had little impact on reducing cases of piracy and armed piracy. Based on the 2017 report on piracy and armed piracy published by the IMB, Nigeria recorded 33 incidents of piracy cases with 7 cases of armed piracy out of 36 cases of piracy and 8 cases of armed piracy in 2016 (ICC International Maritime Bureau, 2020).

Nigeria was listed as a piracy hotspot in an IMO report on the issue that was released in the first quarter of 2018. The IMB reported that Nigeria had 12 instances of armed piracy and 22 incidences of piracy overall. Compared to the previous year, which reported 20 occurrences of piracy, this number showed an increase (Nwangwu et al., 2015).

The Nigerian Navy established partnerships with France, China, Portugal, and three other African navies in 2018 to combat maritime crime in the Gulf of Guinea. Nigeria also hosted the Nigerian Navy International Maritime Conference during same year. Nigeria's cooperation with the military extended from 2016 to the beginning of

2018. Nigeria's response to the rise in criminal activity in Nigerian waterways was this. The Nigerian Army and the Nigerian Air Force are working together to clean Nigeria's waterways in a safe and secure manner, especially in the Niger Delta's environmental waters, which present their own challenges in dealing with maritime crimes, particularly the kidnapping of illegal crews and bunkers that cause pollution (Salau, 2018). Nigeria also works with AFRICOM US, Interpol, and UNODC. The Nigerian government worked together to guarantee the POMO ACT Anti-Piracy Bill 2019 passed quickly before the national assembly (Treatment & Suspect, 2011).

Although Nigeria engaged in a number of cooperative efforts to enhance marine security throughout 2018. A study from the IMB states that Nigeria was responsible for 48 acts of piracy, including 29 cases of ships being boarded, 1 case of a ship being hijacked, 12 cases of armed piracy, and 6 cases of armed pumping experiments (International Maritime Bureau, 2019).

The researcher contends that even though Nigeria implemented the Yaounde Code of Conduct's article content through enhanced naval patrols and strengthened maritime security measures, it has not been successful in lowering instances of piracy and armed robbery there. The high rate of piracy makes this obvious. This indicates that experts have concluded that this implementation has a problem. Inadequate implementation or the less "binding" Yaounde Code of Conduct may be to blame for this rise in piracy and armed robberies in Nigeria.

3.2.2. Make National Legislation That Guarantees The Protection Of The Marine Environment

Nigeria established a number of new laws to lower the number of pirate cases in compliance with article 4 (c) of the Yaounde Code of Conduct, which specifies national-level action steps. This section reads: "National legislation that provides efficient protection of the marine environment" (Onyeji, 2017). The POMO Act, the first anti-piracy law in the Gulf of Guinea region, was passed by Nigeria on June 24, 2019. The POMO Act seeks to stop and deter piracy, armed robbery, and other illegal acts against ships, airplanes, and other marine vessels (Ogbonnaya, 2020b). Nigeria may now bring charges to try offenses under the POMO Act following its enactment. In addition, violators may be found guilty of offences under the Pomo Act and receive punishments from the Federal High Court of Nigeria, including fines of up to N250 million, life in prison, and restitution to the owner (POMO Act, 2019).

In accordance with the POMO Act, 10 pirates were apprehended on July 15, 2019, and each was sentenced to ten years in prison and N200,000 by the Federal High Court of Nigeria in Ikoyi for stealing the merchant ship FV Hailufeng II, which was carrying 20 pirates who had been found guilty under the POMO Act. They were found guilty of three crimes related to piracy that were against sections 3, 10, and 12 of the law (POMO Act, 2019). The Federal High Court of Nigeria in Lagos sentenced 11 pirates to 12 years in prison each on August 18, 2019, for seizing a Chinese fishing boat in international seas off the coast of the Gulf of Guinea. They were found guilty of breaking Section 3 and Section 2 of the Pomo Act (POMO Act, 2019).

The Federal Government of Nigeria updated the Nigeria National Security (NNS) at the end of June 2019, in addition to developing a legal and administrative framework for prosecuting marine offenses. The national policy emphasizes the spread of small guns and light weapons, financial crime, drug and people trafficking, and environmental pollution. exists in Nigeria's marine domain's evils. President Goodluck Jonathan adopted the NNS in 2014 as a comprehensive national strategy document that outlined Nigeria's national security goals in a framework. Nigeria has to revise back the goals of its national security strategy in NNS due to the changing internal and global security environment and the complexity of new concerns including maritime terrorism, kidnappings at sea, insurgency, viral illness outbreaks, and other issues (Vanguard, 2019).

Kidnapping of oil workers, sea piracy, armed robbery at sea, oil theft problems, illegal bunkering, hostage taking, and marine terrorism are all listed as national security threats under the NNS and the POMO Act even though they had not previously been. According to the NNS's goals, this demonstrates an improvement in Nigeria's overall maritime security architecture (Vanguard, 2017).

The IMB observed a decline in pirate cases in Nigeria during the first quarter of 2019. Nigeria registered 14 cases of piracy in 2019 compared to 22 occurrences during the same period in the previous year. The decrease attests to Nigeria's increased efforts to combat maritime crime (International Maritime Bureau, 2019).

As of the end of 2019, Nigeria reportedly continued to decline by 42.6% compared to the previous year. In the first quarter, for the first time Nigeria had no ships hijacked since the first quarter of 1994. The total number of piracy cases throughout 2019 in Nigerian waters was recorded at 35 cases where as many as 23 ships were boarded, 2 ships were hijacked, 1 attempted pirate attack and 9 cases of piracy armed (International Maritime Bureau, 2019).

The Nigerian Navy's operational performance in guarding the EEZ (Exclusive Economic Zone), territory, and internal Economic Zone against maritime crime is evidenced by the ongoing decline in the number of successful attacks. Additionally, the decrease in instances was brought on by the fact that pirates were diverting their criminal activity and changing where they committed armed piracy and other crimes. Nigeria had 11 instances in the first quarter of 2020 through March, compared to 14 during the same period in 2019. Dr. Bashir Jamoh, Director General of NIMASA, stated in an interview with Nigerian Current that the deployment of Deep Blue had been successful in assisting the Nigerian Navy in apprehending possible pirates over the previous two months (Ortise, 2022).

In a Deep Blue rescue operation near April, the Nigerian Navy successfully released 8 crew members who had been kidnapped by pirates from the container ship Tommi Ritscher in Benin. On April 19, as the ship was docked in the port of Cotonou, pirates attacked it. Additionally, 11 crew men were successfully rescued from the ship's defenses and South Niger Delta-based hijackers during the rescue operation (Ortise, 2022).

In some cases, piracy in Nigeria involves armed robbery at sea and detaining crews for ransom. In mid-2020, Deep Blue along with NIMASA arrested 9 defendants in July in connection with the kidnapping of the crew of MV Elobey VI off the coast of Nigeria. Under the POMO Act, a Nigerian Court in Port Harcourt fined 3 hijackers of 44,000 Euros each for hijacking a ship and collecting a ransom of 169,000 Euros in crew kidnapping. The "*Piracy and Armed robbery Against Ship*" report published by the ICC in 2022, Nigerian waters after the launch of the Deep Blue Project continue to experience a decrease in piracy crimes and armed piracy against ships. In the first quarter to March 2021, IMB reported that incidents of piracy and armed robbery decreased by 77% (International Maritime Bureau, 2022).

The report showed that the decline in cases occurred up to 77% compared to the same period in the previous year and 95% compared to the same period in 2018. 4 incidents piracy was reported in the first nine months of 2021, compared to 17 cases in 2020 and 41 in 2018 (International & Bureau, 2021). Based on the above findings, researcher argue that there is a decrease in incidents of piracy and armed piracy occurs due to the transfer of crimes committed by pirates to hostage taking and kidnapping for ransom. The transfer of crime resulted from the POMO Act operating independently of domestic laws governing firearms, kidnapping and money laundering.

The researcher discovered that from a logical standpoint, Nigeria's compliance in drafting the national legislation of the POMO Act to ensure Nigeria's maritime protection was evaluated favorably. The Pomo Act's application in Nigeria still involved militaristic actions, which led to the reasonable, logical reasoning, and regulators' use of expensive consequences like fines or imprisonment as financial disincentives to ensure compliance. The study further contends that this limits its ability to combat the rising criminality in Nigeria's marine sector, which makes implementation of the Yaounde Code of Conduct challenging. A study by Maurice Ogbonnaya, who suggested that the independent passage of the anti-piracy law would not help coordinate piracy responses in the region, which supports the researcher' arguments (Ogbonnaya, 2020a).

The provision of corrupt practices by Nigeria's maritime bodies, where corruption is one of the main causes of pirate incidents, is also not covered by the POMO Act. The POMO Act does not include provisions for articles that include assault, money laundering, and organized crime, despite the fact that the ISS considers piracy to be an organized crime linked to corruption and the arms trade. On the basis of this, the researcher argued that the

POMO Act passed by Nigeria must be in compliance with domestic laws that regulate the crimes of corruption, kidnapping, firearms, and money laundering and strengthen collaboration between relevant agencies in order to achieve compliance in implementing the Yaounde Code of Conduct. Fighting piracy is crucial since Nigeria's marine security is inadequate due to weak institutions and disorderly practices.

3.2.3. Other Countries' Responses to Nigeria Complying with Yaounde Code of Conduct

In addition to Nigeria, there are five other African countries that positively welcome this code of conduct, These five African countries agreed to adopt the Yaoundé Code of Conduct with a view to defending low-level pirate attacks on ships in the Gulf of Guinea. The five countries are Ghana, Angola, Cameroon, the Republic of Benin, and Cote D'Vair. The implementation was contained in a communiqué issued at the end of the two-day meeting of the Economic Community of West African States, (ECOWAS) organized by the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Security Agency, NIMASA (Vanguard, 2021).

Their response to the code of conduct, in their opinion, guarantees collaborative decision-making and follow-up from a response perspective is crucial, countries also agree that relevant regional bodies should institute a framework for regular dialogue. This will help ensure that every area in the region is properly monitored and secured (Vanguard, 2021).

A framework for Maritime Security Architecture in West Africa and the Gulf of Guinea has been established as another African nation's response to the Yaounde Code of Conduct. Its architecture, which has four levels of authority, corresponds to the regional level in West and Central Africa and the areas of responsibility and location of relevant organizations and structures that contribute to marine security. This gives bordering nations encouraging feedback and practical guidance for implementing the code of conduct, which is projected to significantly boost maritime security (L, 2021).

The Yaounde Code of Ethics drew responses from nations in Europe as well. Support given by the European Union to Gulf of Guinea nations experiencing armed conflict is viewed as significant and less alluring. At the national and international levels, Europe supports the demilitarization, demobilization, and reintegration of fighters, security sector reform, and state reconstruction. The European Union also carried out less successful civilian activities in Guinea-Bissau to upgrade security systems in 2009 and 2010. The European Union has not thought about initiating marine operations to stop or stop piracy in the Gulf of Guinea, similar to Operation Atlanta off the coast of Somalia. So that in 2014, the European Union adopted the European Strategy for the Gulf of Guinea to support the objectives of this agreement (Sartre, 2014a).

In addition to other countries there are also many communities of countries such as the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS), and the Gulf of Guinea Commission (GGC) which responded well to the establishment and implementation of this code of conduct. This was marked by the signing of an intraregional agreement at the Yaoundé Heads of State Summit in June 2013 to combat maritime crime in Gulf of Guinea (EEAS, 2021a).

This maritime menace as well as its land-based sources will be lessened as a result of improved regional collaboration and assistance among member nations. In order to achieve this, the EU maintains tight ties with coastal states and continues to work closely with regional groups like ECOWAS and ECCAS. Additionally, it has tight ties with important international institutions like Interpol and the Global Maritime Crimes Program of the UNODC (EEAS, 2021b). Everywhere along the Gulf of Guinea, there is a connection between land-based food and livelihood instability, poverty, disparity in development, and maritime insecurity. And there is a global need for solutions based on greater development and governance. At the Yaoundé Summit on Maritime Safety and Security in the Gulf of Guinea in 2013, the Gulf States of Guinea appeared to favor a different strategy that focused on prevention and even repression at sea (Sartre, 2014b).

From the above discussion, it can be concluded that the responses of countries both in Africa and outside Africa to Nigeria's compliance regarding the implementation of the Yaounde Code of Conduct are very positive. The

implementation of the Yaounde Code of Conduct not only received regional support but also received support from the international community. Researcher argue that this happens as a result of factors that are beneficial to their own country such as economic problems.

4. Conclusion

According to the findings of the analysis performed by researcher, Nigeria complies with the Yaounde Code of Conduct in cases of piracy and armed piracy in Nigeria from 2016 to 2021. Nigeria actively develops and puts into effect national marine security measures to guard against any type of illegal activity. Through the use of national processes implemented from 2016 to 2021, Nigeria continues to pursue the need to improve maritime security and traffic in order to protect maritime commerce and prevent international maritime trade bottlenecks.

However, the oppressive measures Nigeria is adopting to abide by the Yaounde Code of Conduct have not shown to effectively decrease piracy incidents since they do not address the underlying reasons why it occurs. Researcher discovered that the economic, social, and environmental conditions created in Nigeria are to blame for the piracy that takes place there. The existence of conflicts and chaos between the government and the people of Nigeria, favorable geographic location, widespread poverty, weak legal and judicial systems, ineffective law enforcement, a permissive political climate, cultural acceptance, and promises of rewards are a few examples of these conditions. Given that piracy primarily originates on land as a result of corrupt government officials, a bad system of government, and the aggression of economic privatization, particularly against the oil and gas sector, piracy also involves other international crimes, such as money laundering.

Due to the invisible interconnectedness in the international system, changes within the system tend to occur in a repetitive pattern and have a significant impact on the states within the system. On the other hand, state behavior is guided by the natural characteristics of each leader or by the "invisible hand" caused by the anarchic international system (Juned et al., 2019). The tendency to accumulate power, either through defensive or offensive realist approaches, will always be present in any decision made in any situation for the sake of certain interests (Williams & Elman, 2020).

Researcher discovered that the ineffectiveness of the Nigerian state and administration soon contributed to a lack of security on land that easily spread to maritime security and gave rise to maritime crimes like piracy and armed robbery. Unemployed members of underprivileged communities with limited economic opportunities frequently use such piracy as a source of income.

Nigeria's oppressive priorities overlook the structural and economic issues brought on by corruption in the government. The emphasis on repression also resulted in the diverting of funds for marine militaristic conquests, which prevented funding for capital projects in fields related to human development including jobs, health, and education. Therefore, implementing such militaristic methods won't be successful in permanently resolving the issue of piracy and armed piracy. Researcher' investigation revealed that the Yaounde Code of Ethics' application is consistent with the accepted theory of compliance, in which the code of ethics was genuinely put into practice and followed by the parties involved in this instance. However, due to the reputation and lack of a strong legal position, the resulting "level of compliance" is not very significant.

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